

ANALYSIS OF TEACHING SKILLS POSSESSED BY TEACHERS IN SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN IMO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

The study investigated the teaching skills possessed by senior secondary school teachers in Imo State Nigeria. The study was carried out in secondary schools in two local Government areas of the state. Based on the objectives of the study, two research questions and a hypothesis guided the study. The descriptive survey research design was adopted in carrying out the study. A sample of 387 teachers from 16 Government owned secondary schools from the area was selected for the study through purposive sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a researchers' made rating scale with reliability coefficient of 0.81 determined using Cronbach's alpha formula. Data generated from the study was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions while the hypothesis was analyzed using t-test statistical tool tested at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the study revealed that, the teaching skills possessed by teachers in these areas include; set induction skills, closure skills, use of examples and illustration skills and questioning skills. Based on the result of the

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study it was recommended that secondary school teachers should be trained and retrained periodically on teaching skills that will enhance their effectiveness.

Keywords: teacher, teaching skills, teaching effectiveness

1. Introduction

Teachers are saddled with the responsibility of impacting knowledge to learners at every level of education. Ighohiro (2012) stated that, teachers are those who mold student character, personality and show students the right direction to success. A functional education is hinged on a well-trained and retrained teacher in the classroom. Rahayu (2017) stated that the main factor that decides the quality of education is the teacher so that the quality of teachers should be in the main focus to enhance the quality of education in our country. Every system is adjudged by the value of its products and services and in the case of education, the core product is well tutored learner who possesses specific teaching skills and knowledge with refined behavior that enable him function effectively in the society (Onye & Ajuzie, 2018).

It is the teacher who should direct, organize and encourage the students to become agents of change in any society. Ryan and Cooper cited in Obidike (2017) noted that a teacher must demonstrate a repertoire of teaching skills that are believed to facilitate students learning and must display attitude that foster learning and genuine human relationship. According to Ullah, Farooq and Memon (2008) preparation of teachers for effective teaching needs pedagogical and interpersonal skills. This implies that, a pedagogical skill possessed by a teacher determines his level of effectiveness. Teachers can play their role effectively only when they are well trained (Sharma, 2000). Sanjaya (2009) stated that teachers' basic teaching skills are needed in order to make teachers be able to do their role in managing learning process so that learning process can run smoothly and efficiently. Basic teaching skills are an absolute requirement for teacher to be able to implement various lesson strategies (Rahayu, 2017). Teachers are in charge of choosing and deciding materials, strategies, methods, media, and instruments for evaluation in performing learning process to achieve education result which has high quality and has been accepted by teachers' ethic code (Rahayu, 2017)

Teaching skills originated from Allen and his group in the 1960's in Stanford University, United States of America (Ike, 2003; Ifegbo, 2012; Iwu, Ajuzie & Nzeakor, 2013, 2018) respectively. These scholars according to the above authors observed that it was the push to look out for those things that would contribute to effective teaching and learning and to replace the traditional methods of exposing teachers to classroom teaching that led to isolation of these teacher behaviours. At Stanford University then, in an attempt to isolate the appropriate teacher behaviour, teachers were asked to teach. In the process of teaching, other teachers were observing them. In this way, teacher behaviours or teaching skills were identified and isolated. These skills were then accepted as appropriate teaching skills a professional teacher should acquire for

teaching effectiveness and efficiency. However, other behaviours that were genetically oriented and good for entertainment were not selected for classroom instruction. It was these identified and isolated teacher behaviors that were observed and practiced that gave teaching a professional background.

According to Kyriacou (2007), teaching skills are measured and coherent activity performed by teachers in order to make students study. It is also regarded as the strategies that teachers employ which facilitate students' learning and which are acknowledged by those competent as being teaching skills. Okoye and Aneto (2010), Iwu, Ajuzie & Nzeakor (2013) citing Achuonye (2002), Umoren and Ogong (2007), stated that pedagogical skills or teaching skills are those positive behaviors of a teacher which promote the efficiency and effectiveness of classroom instruction these includes;

- **Set induction:** this is a skill used to arouse the interest of learners, create an atmosphere of curiosity and motivation in any learning environment. This skill energizes, directs and sustains the learner's interest for the period of lesson delivery.
- **Questioning:** this is an activity that arouses the curiosity and mental activity of a learner. A teacher should master this skill in such a way that he can use it at will in the classroom instruction. It is highly recommended to teachers ever since Socrates first used it to draw out ideas from learning. Questioning skills are categorized into higher order cognitive questioning, lower order cognitive questioning, probing questions and divergent questions.
- **Use of examples and illustration:** it is a skill that helps the teacher to use concrete and verbal references in the class in order to positively influence the learners. It helps the memory to store learning and minimize forgetting.
- **Planned repetition:** this skill is employed to help the learner assimilate what is being taught as the teacher repeats himself/herself in a more planned manner during instructional delivery.
- **Stimulus variation:** this skill strikes the learning senses of the learners such as the eyes, ears, mouth, smell and tactile.
- **Non-verbal communication:** the teacher adopts this skill by using signals via body movements in order to attract the attention of the learners in the class.
- **Reinforcement:** it is a deliberate attempt by the teacher to change the behaviour of the learner. This action of the teacher can be positive or negative reinforcement. Reinforcement is positive when the action of the teacher increases the probability of the response occurring again and again. Such actions of the teacher include "very good" "well done" and such actions that will help the learner to perform better. Negative reinforcement is the teacher's actions for correction of an unwanted behavior. This is done by giving punishment, withholding rewards or application of corrective feedback.
- **Closure:** it is the skill that often marks the end of a lesson. However, it may be used anywhere along the lesson for the purpose of rounding up any unit of

instruction (Iwu, 2001; Ike, 2003; Achuonye, 2002; Ifegbo, 2012; Iwu, Ajuzie & Nzeakor, 2013, Okoye and Aneto 2010).

Since teaching is an individual art, it is very difficult to find two or more teachers who teach in an identical way. The job involves the teacher's knowledge of the subject and subject matter he teaches, the skills he uses and his personality. Therefore, an efficient teacher has to try out several teaching skills in different situations so as to realize his talent and potentials. The merits of each of these teaching skills in bringing out a would-be quality teacher in the classroom cannot be over emphasized (Ajuzie & Chukwu, 2016).

2. Statement of the Problem

The most efficient process to national development globally is in the deliberate improvement of its population. This is to improve its human capital capacity development. Thus, the most valuable of all capital is the investment in human beings whose process renders education and training very critical. It is germane to say that there is need to train and retrain the post basic teachers in the Imo State of Nigeria with a view to actualizing vision 20:2020. The retraining of the teachers is very important because they impact knowledge to the students who in turn apply their acquired knowledge in the development of the nation. This has become pertinent as observations and results of students performance in public examinations has indicated that post basic students are not properly taught. This is suspected to have resulted from the inefficient application of teaching skills by the teachers at the secondary school level.

This study was carried out to investigate the teaching skills possessed by secondary school teachers in Imo State.

2.1 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the teaching skills possessed by teachers at the secondary school level. Specifically the study will determine:

- 1) the teaching skills which are possessed by senior secondary school teachers;
- 2) the difference between the teaching skills possessed by senior secondary school teachers in rural and urban areas of Imo State.

2.2 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- 1) What are the teaching skills possessed by senior secondary school teachers?
- 2) What is the difference between the response mean of teachers on teaching skills possessed by senior secondary school teachers in rural and urban areas?

2.3 Hypothesis

The hypothesis listed below was formulated to guide the study.

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the response mean of teachers on the teaching skills possessed by senior secondary school teachers in rural urban areas.

3. Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design to determine the teaching skills possessed by senior secondary school teachers. The population of the study consists of all the one thousand and eighty seven (1087) teachers from twenty four (24) Government owned secondary schools in Owerri municipal council and Orlu Local Government areas of Imo State, Nigeria. A sample of three hundred and eighty seven (387) teachers consisting of two hundred and fifty one (251) urban and one hundred and twenty six (126) rural teachers were purposively selected from 16 Government owned secondary schools from the area. The instrument for data collection was a researchers' made rating scale titled "Teaching Skills Possessed by Teachers in Senior Secondary Schools (TSPTSSS). It was divided into two parts, part A dealt with respondents demographic variables while, part B dealt with teaching skills required from the teachers. The responses required from the teachers ranged as follows; Strongly Agree(SA)=4, Agree(A)=3, Disagree(D)=2 and Strongly Disagree(SD)=1. To determine the reliability of the instrument, 30copies were administered to teachers outside the study sample but with the same characteristics, their responses were analyzed using Cronbach alpha formula which gave a reliability coefficient of 0.81 which was considered appropriate for the study. The instrument was administered to the respondents on face to face basis by the researchers through the help of their head teachers after explaining the objectives of the study to them. They were assured of the confidentiality of the information given. They instruments were filled out and collected on the spot by the researchers and the entire process lasted for two weeks. The data generated was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions. Any response means within and above the criterion mean of 2.50 was accepted while any below the criterion mean was rejected. The hypothesis was analyzed using t-test statistical tool tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question One: What are the teaching skills possessed by the teachers of senior secondary schools?

Table 1: Teaching skills possessed by teacher

S/N	Item	Mean $\bar{x}$	SD	Remark
1	Teachers are equipped with set induction skills.	3.25	0.72	Accept / Possessed
2	Teachers possessed closure skills.	3.16	0.81	Accept / Possessed
3	Stimulus variation skills are possessed by secondary schools teachers.	2.32	1.25	Reject / Not Possessed
4	Non-verbal communication skills are possessed by teachers.	2.12	1.32	Reject / Not Possessed
5	Teachers apply use of examples and illustrations in	3.20	0.91	Accept / Possessed

	teaching.			
6	Planned repetition skills are possessed by secondary school teachers.	2.30	1.28	Reject / Not Possessed
7	Questioning skills are possessed by teachers.	3.22	0.95	Accept / Possessed
8	Use of reinforcement skills are possessed by teachers.	2.14	1.41	Reject / Not Possessed

Table 1 shows that items 1, 2, 5 and 7 were accepted as they had response mean greater than the criterion mean which indicates that, they are the teaching skills possessed by secondary school teachers. However, items 3, 4, 6 and 8 were rejected as they had response mean less than the criterion mean.

Research question 2: What is the difference between the response mean of teachers on teaching skills possessed by senior secondary school teachers in rural and urban areas?

Table 2: t-test analysis of difference between mean responses of teachers in rural and urban areas, on teaching skills possessed by the teachers

Teachers	N	Mean	SD Diff	t-cal	Df	t _{0.05}
Rural	126	3.17	0.950.19	0.112		
Urban	251	2.98	1.03		1488	1.65

Table 2 shows that teachers in the rural secondary schools had mean response of 3.17 with standard deviation of 0.95 while their urban counterparts had mean response of 2.98 with standard deviation of 1.03, these gave a mean difference of 0.19 in favour of the rural teachers.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the response mean of teachers on the teaching skills possessed by senior secondary school teachers in rural urban areas.

Table 2 shows that the calculated t-value (0.112) is less than the table value 1.65 at degree freedom 1488 and 0.05 level of significance. Based on the result, the null hypothesis is upheld at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that, there is no significant difference between the teaching skills possessed by teachers of senior secondary schools in rural and urban areas.

4. Discussion of Findings

The result of the study revealed that senior secondary school teachers possess the following teaching skills, set induction, closure, use of examples and illustrations and questioning skills. The skills were noted to have response mean greater than the criterion mean and were accepted as skills possessed by the teachers. Further statistical analysis showed that, there was no significant difference between the teaching skills possessed by secondary school teachers in rural and urban areas in Imo State. This implies that secondary school teachers at urban and rural areas possess the same

teaching skills. This result is in-line with the findings of Ajuzie and Chukwu (2016) which revealed that, the skills of set induction, use of examples and illustration, questioning and closure were the most frequently used by teachers.

4.1 Conclusion

The result of the study revealed that teaching skills possessed by senior secondary school teachers in Imo State includes, set induction, closure, use of examples and illustrations and questioning skills. The result of the study revealed that the possession of these teaching skills was not affected by school locations.

4.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Teachers at secondary school level should arm themselves with teaching skills as to enhance effective teaching.
2. Only qualified and well trained teachers should be employed to teach at the secondary schools as to enable them apply the appropriate teaching skills in the classroom.
3. Seminars, workshops and symposia should always be organized by the Government NGOs and School Managers to train and retrain teachers on teaching skills.

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